

Private wealth management platform for financial relationship managers

We redesigned the CRM tool that helps users initiate and manage their clients investment journey by using advisory algorithms to identify the most suitable investments to meet their clients' evolving financial goals and investment appetite

- UX Audit
- Task Flow Optimization
- Navigational structure Redesign
- Wireframing
- Visual Design

The Engagement

Strategic Changes for Immediate impact

- Identified user pain points that defined the product strategy: 40% Increase in sales revenue in 2024.
- Rapid Evaluation of the current product and identification of improvements - near term and long term

Fast go-to-market of Keystone features

Improved access to key tools

- Reduced the effort in finding tools that user needs on a recurring basis to conduct administrative tasks with a right hand navigation panel. The design made the user journey 3x more efficient.
- 3x more efficient

Streamlined Onboarding

Streamlined the process of creating new profiles and onboarding users. Introduced a progressive bar to help user estimate their journey.

Delight in Exploration

Inducing delight in exploring investment opportunities by creating an engaging and intuitive Exploratory page which used Ai and advanced machine learning to recommend personalised products for every unique client's appetite and past purchases

Structural changes to the product for future proofing.

- Introduction of data visualization and interaction patterns which increased information consumption
- Redefined the product experience from an enterprise to customer facing application
- Standardized Design System which lead to code reusability

Source: <https://www.copods.co/case-studies/wealth-management/>